

The Nenitzescu Reaction : Synthesis of 1-Alkyl(or Aryl)-3-Benzoyl-5-Hydroxy-2-Phenylindole Derivatives

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Some 3-N-alkyl (or aryl) amino-1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-ones were prepared and condensed with 1,4-benzoquinone and 1,4-naphthoquinone to give 1-alkyl (or aryl)-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles which were methylated to the corresponding 5-methoxyindoles. Studies of the IR spectra of the above compounds reveal the existence of intermolecular H-bonding in 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxyindoles.

THE Nenitzescu¹ reaction is a versatile and widely applied method for the synthesis of various 5-hydroxyindole derivatives.² Grinev *et al.*³ extended this reaction for the preparation of 3-acetyl-5-hydroxy-2-methyl indoles from the corresponding acetyl acetone imines. In our laboratory, Betkerur and Siddappa⁴ have condensed various ethyl β -aminocinnamates with 1,4-quinones in suitable solvent, leading to ethyl 5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole-3-carboxylates. Continued interest in this reaction prompted us to undertake the synthesis of the title compounds, using 3-N-substituted amino-1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-ones in place of ethyl β -aminocinnamates.

Dibenzoyl methane⁵ was reacted with *n*-propyl amine, *n*-butyl amine, *iso*-butyl amine, benzyl amine and aniline to get 3-*n*-propylamino-, 3-*n*-butylamino-, 3-*iso*-butylamino-, 3-benzylamino and 3-anilino-1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-ones (Ia-e). The PMR spectral results of (Id) show that these aminopropenones (Ia-e) exist exclusively in an intramolecular H-bonded aminoform.

The aminopropenone (Ia) was condensed with 1,4-benzoquinone in ethanolic solution to obtain the desired 1-*n*-propyl-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (IIa). The condensation of (Ia) with 1,4-naphthoquinone in glacial acetic acid furnished 1-*n*-propyl-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenyl-1H-benz[g]indole (IVa). Similarly, the condensation of (Ib-e) with 1,4-benzoquinone gave the respective indole derivatives (IIB-e) and the benzindole derivatives (IVb-d) were obtained by the condensation of (Ib-d) with 1,4-naphthoquinone. These hydroxyindole derivatives (IIa-e) and (IVa-d) were methylated with dimethyl sulphate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate in a

mixture of suitable solvents to obtain the corresponding methoxyindole derivatives (IIIA-e) and (V-a-d).

The PMR spectrum of (IIc) is in good agreement with the structure assigned. The *iso*-butyl group attached to indole N gave a doublet at 9.4 τ , a multiplet centered at 8.15 τ and another doublet at 6.15 τ corresponding to the protons of two methyls, central methine and methylene groups, respectively. The value of coupling constant (J) is about 7 Hz. The aromatic region (2.5-3.2 τ) revealed the presence of twelve protons. A broad peak shown at 1.8 τ corresponds to two protons. On further dilution this broad peak was split into two signals having different chemical shifts. Of the two, the doublet (J 2.5 Hz) observed at 1.8 τ is assigned to C-4 proton and a broad signal at 2.14 τ to the C-5 hydroxyl proton which vanished on D₂O treatment. The value of coupling constant (J 2.5 Hz) signified *meta*-coupling with C-6 proton and it was also noted that the C-4 proton signal (1.8 τ) was independent of concentration. The signal for the C-4 proton of 2-phenyl-5-hydroxyindole derivatives possessing vacant 3-position was generally observed^{4c} in the range of 3.11-3.18 τ . Hence, the paramagnetic shift of C-4 proton signal of (IIc) to such low field (1.8 τ) might be attributable to the deshielding effect imposed by the carbonyl function⁶ of C-3 benzoyl substituent on this proton.

The studies pertaining to H-bonding in indole derivatives are few. Tanner⁷ reported 3-acylindoles to exist as strongly H-bonded polymers in the solid state on the basis of the shifts shown by NH and carbonyl bands to higher frequencies upon dilution in tetrahydrofuran. The increase displayed by the carbonyl bands (1640-1620 cm⁻¹) on N-methylation of 3-acylindoles⁸ is also an indication of strong H-bonding that persists in this type of compounds. However, there is paucity of literature regarding the study of

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R =

a; $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$

c; $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$

b; $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_3$

d; $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

e; $-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$

H-bonding in 1-substituted-3-acyl-5-hydroxyindoles. Grinev and co-workers⁹ have reported the carbonyl bands of 1-aryl-2-methyl-3-acyl-5-hydroxyindoles at 1594–1608 cm^{-1} but needs explanation.

In the course of our investigation, the IR spectra of 1-alkyl (or aryl)-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles (IIa–e) and their benzindole analogues (IVa–d) showed ketonic and hydroxyl bands in the range of 1570–1597 cm^{-1} and 3077–3200 cm^{-1} , respectively. But, these ketonic bands at unusually low frequencies (1570–1597 cm^{-1}) shifted to higher frequencies (1613–1623 cm^{-1}) on methylating the C-5 hydroxyl function (Table 3). This phenomenon suggests to infer that very strong intermolecular H-bonding persists in 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles which vanished on methylation. Additional proof to substantiate this inference was provided by the higher frequencies (1605–1615 cm^{-1}) shown by the C-3

benzoyl function of 1-substituted-3-benzoyl-4-arylthiomethyl-5-hydroxyl-2-phenylindoles.⁹ Since, the C-5 hydroxyl function is involved in intramolecular H-bonding with the ether sulphur in case of these 4-arylthioethers, the possibility of intermolecular H-bonding is ruled out. Consequently, the ketonic bands are observed at higher frequencies (1604–1615 cm^{-1}) than the ketonic bands (1570–1597 cm^{-1}) of their precursors (i.e., 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole analogues).

Among the various 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy indoles (IIa–e and IVa–d), 1-*iso*-butyl-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (IIc) is the only compound which showed moderate solubility in chloroform. Hence the IR spectra of (IIc) in chloroform were recorded at different concentrations (g./vol.; 1–0.33%). The hydroxyl and ketonic bands showed the shifts from

3270 to 3310 cm^{-1} and from 1610 to 1630 cm^{-1} , respectively, upon dilution. The concentration dependency of C-5 hydroxyl proton absorption was also noted in the PMR spectrum of (IIc) in CDCl_3 solution. This proton signal at 1.8 τ moved to 2.14 τ as the dilution of the solution increased and disappeared on D_2O treatment. Siddappa and Betkerur^{4c} have described the C-5 hydroxyl proton signals of 1-substituted-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles in CDCl_3 solutions in the range of 4.51–4.98 τ . But, even at dilute solution of (IIc) the C-5 hydroxyl proton signal was observed at lower field (2.14 τ) which indicated the presence of C-3 benzoyl function in 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles as crucial and is definitely involved in intermolecular H-bonding with C-5 hydroxyl.

Very recently, Kovac *et al.*¹⁰ have reported the presence of a strong intermolecular H-bonding in 2-hydroxy-8-acetylnaphthalene and they have proposed the existence of this compound as a H-bonded dimer in a spatially favourable 16-membered ring system. As these 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles and their benzindole analogues are also nearly similar to 2-hydroxy-8-acetylnaphthalene, it seems reasonable to postulate that these may also exist as dimers in a spatially possible 16-membered ring system.

However, at this stage the probable existence of these 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles and their benzindole analogues as the extensive H-bonded polymers in the solid state could not be also ruled out.

Experimental

3-n-Propylamino-1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one (Ia) :

n-Propyl amine (3 g.) was added in small portions to dibenzoyl methane (10 g.) with external cooling and left at room temperature for 1 hr. A catalytic quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 drops) was added to the mixture and heated at 90°–95° for 18 hr. It was cooled, extracted with ether, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and the solvent removed. The residue on distillation under diminished pressure gave the *aminopropenone* (Ia) as a

pale yellow oil (8 g.), b.p. 200°–205°/4–5 mmHg; (Found : N, 5.33. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}$ requires N, 5.28%).

3-n-Butylamino-1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one (Ib) :

Following the procedure described for (Ia), dibenzoyl methane (10 g.) was condensed with *n*-butyl amine (4 g.) at 80°–90° to yield (Ib) as a pale yellow oil (7.5 g.), b.p. 220°–225°/4–5 mmHg; (Found : N, 5.10. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}$ requires N, 5.01%).

3-iso-Butylamino-1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one (Ic) :

Dibenzoyl methane (10 g.) was reacted with *iso*-butyl amine (4 g.) at 80°–90°, according to the procedure given for (Ia) to yield the *aminopropenone* (Ic) as a pale yellow oil (7.8 g.), b.p. 235°–240°/4–5 mmHg; (Found : N, 4.89. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{21}\text{NO}$ requires N, 5.01%).

3-Benzylamino-1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one (Id) :

Dibenzoyl methane (10 g.) was condensed with benzyl amine (5.25 g.) at 90°–100° according to the procedure described for (Ia) to yield a solid which was twice crystallised from rectified spirit to get the pure *aminopropenone* (Id) as pale yellow thick plates (9 g.), m.p. 98° (lit¹¹ 98°–99°); $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ cm^{-1} 2976b (NH) and 1592s (C = O); PMR (CDCl_3 , TMS) τ 5.6 -CH₂-Ph (2H, d, J 7 Hz); 4.18 $\overset{\text{H}}{\text{C}}=\text{C}-\text{Ph}$ (1H, S); –1.6 -HN-CH₂Ph (1H, broad signal); 2.0–2.9 ArH (15H, m); (Found : C, 84.16; H, 5.90; N, 4.67. $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{19}\text{NO}$ requires C, 84.31; H, 6.11; N, 4.47%).

3-Anilino-1,3-diphenyl-2-propen-1-one (Ie) :

Following the procedure described for (Ia), dibenzoyl methane (10 g.) was condensed with freshly distilled aniline (4.2 g.) at 165°–170° to give an yellow solid. It was twice crystallised from ethanol to obtain the pure *aminopropenone* (Ie) as pale yellow plates (7 g.), m.p. 110° (Found : C, 84.19; H, 5.47; N, 4.74. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}$ requires C, 84.25; H, 5.72; N, 4.68%).

1-n-Propyl-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindole (IIa) :

The *aminopropenone* (Ia) (20 g.) dissolved in absolute ethanol (100 ml.) was added to 1,4-benzoquinone (9 g.) in ethanol (200 ml.) with shaking. The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature for 1 hr., then heated at reflux for 4–6 hr. and set aside overnight. The solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure to dryness and the residue was purified from benzene and then twice crystallised from dioxane to get the pure hydroxyindole (IIa).

Similarly, the condensation of (Ib–e) with 1,4-benzoquinone gave the corresponding hydroxyindoles (IIb–e) which are described in Table 1.

PMR spectrum of (IIc) in CDCl_3 (TMS), τ 9.4 (6H, d, J 7Hz, two CH₃); 8.15 (1H, m, –CH <); 6.15 (2H, d, J 7Hz, –CH₂–); 1.80 (2H, broad peak, 5-OH and 4-H); 2.5–3.2 (12H, m, ArH); on dilution, 1.80 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, 4-H); 2.14 (1H, broad signal, 5-OH); on D_2O exchange, the signal at 2.14 (OH) disappeared.

TABLE 1—1-SUBSTITUTED-3-BENZOYL-5-HYDROXY-2-PHENYL-INDOLES (IIa-e) AND THEIR BENZINDOLE ANALOGUES (IVa-d)

Compd.	Formula	M.P. °C	Yield (%)	TLC* Rf value	Analysis (%)						UV Spectra** λ_{max} nm (log ϵ)
					Found			Requires.			
					C	H	N	C	H	N	
IIa	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ NO ₂	242	29	0.314	81.21	6.05	3.98	81.10	5.96	3.94	227(4.391), 275(4.204) & 325(4.097)
IIb	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ NO ₂	255	30	0.345	81.16	6.32	3.52	81.27	6.27	3.79	235(4.313), 265(4.247) & 330(3.986)
IIc	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ NO ₂	221	31	0.337	81.32	6.16	3.97	81.27	6.27	3.79	230(4.291), 265(4.201) & 330(4.056)
IIId	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ NO ₂	234	19	0.384	83.23	5.10	3.55	83.35	5.25	3.47	235(4.525), 270(4.346) & 330(4.206)
IIe	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ NO ₂	285	7	0.407	83.40	5.03	3.56	83.27	4.92	3.60	230(4.443), 270(4.327) & 325(4.187)
IVa	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ NO ₂	301	32	0.454	82.81	5.85	3.51	82.94	5.74	3.45	225(4.430), 275(4.665) & 355(3.920)
IVb	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ NO ₂	245	34	0.494	83.23	6.23	3.42	83.03	6.01	3.34	227(4.384) & 270(4.610)
IVc	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ NO ₂	272	33	0.483	83.18	6.19	3.52	83.03	6.01	3.34	225(4.491) & 275(4.706)
IVd	C ₃₂ H ₂₃ NO ₂	262	31	0.540	85.01	5.29	3.22	84.74	5.11	3.09	220(4.345) & 265(4.566)

* Silica gel G plates, benzene-ethyl acetate (9 : 2).

** The UV spectra were recorded in ethanol solution except (IIa), for which dioxane was used.

TABLE 2—1-SUBSTITUTED-3-BENZOYL-5-METHOXY-2-PHENYL-INDOLES (IIIa-e) AND THEIR BENZINDOLE ANALOGUES (Va-d)

Compound	Formula	M.P. °C	TLC* (Rf value)	Analysis(%)						UV spectra (ethanol) λ_{max} nm (log ϵ)
				Found			Requires			
				C	H	N	C	H	N	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
IIIa	C ₂₅ H ₂₃ NO ₂	95	0.517	81.36	6.34	3.69	81.27	6.27	3.79	225(4.446), 270(4.250) & 330(4.107)
2,4-DNP of IIIa	C ₃₁ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₅	254	—	—	—	13.05	—	—	12.74	—
IIIb	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ NO ₂	98	0.54	81.59	6.28	3.48	81.43	6.57	3.65	222(4.424), 270(4.214) & 325(4.067)
2,4-DNP of IIIb	C ₃₂ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₅	233	—	—	—	12.21	—	—	12.43	—
IIIc	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ NO ₂	127	0.506 ^a	81.21	6.68	3.64	81.43	6.57	3.65	230(4.300), 265(4.215) & 335(3.944)
2,4-DNP of IIIc	C ₃₂ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₅	240	—	—	—	12.48	—	—	12.43	—
IIId	C ₂₉ H ₂₃ NO ₂	118	0.625 ^b	83.62	5.36	3.29	83.43	5.55	3.35	222(4.436), 265(4.224) & 330(4.103)
2,4-DNP of IIId	C ₃₅ H ₂₇ N ₅ O ₅	244	—	—	—	11.78	—	—	11.72	—
IIIe	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ NO ₂	172	0.605	83.24	5.32	3.63	83.35	5.25	3.47	222(4.417), 260(4.261) & 325(4.058)
2,4-DNP of IIIe	C ₃₄ H ₂₅ N ₅ O ₅	281	—	—	—	11.73	—	—	12.00	—
Va	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ NO ₂	157	0.575	83.19	6.23	3.41	83.03	6.01	3.34	225(4.393) & 270(4.590)
2,4-DNP of Va	C ₃₅ H ₂₉ N ₅ O ₅	282	—	—	—	11.57	—	—	11.68	—
Vb	C ₃₀ H ₂₇ NO ₂	161	0.577	83.29	6.07	3.14	83.11	6.28	3.23	225(4.370), 265(4.600) & 310(4.260)
2,4-DNP of Vb	C ₃₆ H ₃₁ N ₅ O ₅	268	—	—	—	11.55	—	—	11.41	—
Vc	C ₃₀ H ₂₇ NO ₂	193	0.588	83.07	6.39	3.26	83.11	6.28	3.23	225(4.330), 265(4.539) & 307(4.192)
2,4-DNP of Vc	C ₃₆ H ₃₁ N ₅ O ₅	250	—	—	—	11.46	—	—	11.41	—
Vd	C ₃₃ H ₂₆ NO ₂	226	0.624	85.02	5.35	3.08	84.77	5.39	3.00	220(4.390) & 265(4.580)

* Silicagel G plates, benzene-ethyl acetate (8 : 1); ^a, Benzene-ethyl acetate (4 : 1); ^b, Benzene-ethyl acetate (11 : 1).

1-*n*-Propyl-3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenyl-1*H*-benz[*g*]indole (IVa) :

A solution of aminopropenone (Ia) (20 g.) in glacial acetic acid (100 ml) was added in small portions to 1,4-naphthoquinone (10 g.) in acetic acid (200 ml.) with shaking. The mixture was heated at 50°–60° for 5–8 hr. and set aside overnight. The separated solid was collected, washed with fresh acetic acid (50 ml.) and crystallised from nitrobenzene to furnish the pure *hydroxybenzindole* (IVa).

TABLE 3—1-SUBSTITUTED-3-BENZOYL-5-HYDROXY-2-PHENYL-INDOLES (IIa-e AND IVa-d) AND THEIR 5-METHOXY ANALOGUES (IIIa-e AND Va-d)

Compound KBr pellet	1-Substituent	IR stretching frequencies (cm ⁻¹)	
		νOH	νC = O
IIa +IIIa	<i>n</i> -Propyl "	3145b absent	1587s 1615s
IIb IIIb	<i>n</i> -Butyl "	3106b absent	1592m, 1570s 1618s
IIc IIIc	<i>iso</i> -Butyl "	3175b absent	1592m, 1580s 1623s
IId IIId	Benzyl "	3155b absent	1590s 1613s
+IIe IIIe	Phenyl "	3200b absent	1595s 1616s
IVa +Va	<i>n</i> -Propyl "	3125b absent	1592s 1620s
IVb +Vb	<i>n</i> -Butyl "	3077b absent	1597s 1620s
+IVc +Vc	<i>iso</i> -Butyl "	3140b absent	1588s 1618s
IVd Vd	Benzyl "	3125b absent	1587s 1613s

† The IR spectra were recorded in nujol mull;
s = strong; m = medium.

Similarly, the condensation of (Ib–d) with 1,4-naphthoquinone yielded the respective hydroxybenzindoles (IVb–d) which are reported in Table 1.

General procedure for the methylation of various 3-benzoyl-5-hydroxy-2-phenylindoles (IIa–e and IVa–d) to the corresponding 5-methoxyindoles (IIIa–e and Va–d) :

To the hydroxyindoles (2 g.) dissolved in a mixture of dry acetone (50 ml.) and benzene (50 ml.) or dry xylene (50 ml.) and dioxane (50 ml.) or dry nitrobenzene (50 ml.) and dioxane (50 ml.) depending upon their solubility, was added anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) and then dimethyl sulphate (2 ml.).

The mixture was heated under reflux with stirring for about 15–20 hr., cooled and filtered. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure to give the residue which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether to get pure *methoxyindoles* in varying yields (75–85%).

All these methoxyindoles (IIa–e and Va–d) and their 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone derivatives (2,4-DNP) are described in Table 2.

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